

Versum – Fluor

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Versum is a realtime three dimensional audiovisual composition system that I programmed. It forces both the composer and the audience to see the music and listen to the visuals. The audience sees and hears the compositions that have been made in Versum as a journey through an abstract space in which sound-emitting three dimensional shapes (Entities) form the building blocks of a musical piece. The moving virtual camera through which we see these Entities can travel in any speed in any direction. Entities which are to the right of the camera will also be heard on the right and those that are above or behind the camera will also be heard from above or behind, if enough speakers are used and placed in the right positions. Compositions which are being heard and seen are thus live three dimensional audiovisual journeys being traveled. All the aspects of this journey can be created and modified in realtime: both the path of the journey and the Entities which the virtual camera meets during its travels can be changed according to the wishes of the composer. The composition Fluor is based on several experiments with the esthetical and technical properties of this system, which were eventually combined into one coherent piece. As the composition progresses, we see how the scales of the audiovisual structures become larger and how the structures themselves become more and more organized into more musical and geometrical patterns.